

Influence Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management on the Organizational Performance of the Army Headquarters Mediated by Organizational Commitment

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 04 February 2026	The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management on organizational performance, mediated by organizational commitment at the Army Headquarters. The research method used in this study is hypothesis testing. This quantitative study used a questionnaire administered to 177 officers and leaders at the Army Headquarters. Data analysis used SPSS and PLS 3.20 software with a multivariate Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis method. The results of this study indicate a significant and positive influence of transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management on organizational performance. Transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management significantly and positively impact organizational commitment. The indirect effect of transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management on organizational performance, mediated by organizational commitment, is significant and positive. The implications of this research are that transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management can optimally support the organizational performance of the Army Headquarters, and this requires government attention in the process of improving policy formulation. Transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management indicate that the results of this study significantly strengthen the influence of transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management on the organizational performance of the Army Headquarters. Organizational commitment, as a mediator between transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management, can improve the organizational performance of the Army Headquarters.
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INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian Army (TNI AD) is one of the main components of national defense established by Government Decree in accordance with Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian National Army. The TNI AD has a major responsibility in maintaining the sovereignty, territorial integrity, and safety of the Indonesian nation. In carrying out its duties, the TNI AD is required to always be professional, objective, and have high integrity, so that every soldier has a strong character in behaving and acting in every situation of carrying out duties (Mabesad, 2019). This professionalism can only be realized if all organizational units within the TNI AD are able to manage the organization

maturely, have a superior mentality, and implement a human resource management system (HRD) that is based on a merit and accountable system.

In facing an increasingly complex and competitive strategic environment, the Army Headquarters (Mabesad) needs to improve its organizational adaptability to remain relevant and maintain optimal performance. Organizational performance is a vital indicator of the success or failure of an organization, including within the Army Headquarters. Achieving organizational goals depends heavily on harmonious cooperation between personnel, as well as their ability to collaborate and innovate. Although the Army Headquarters is supported by adequate facilities,

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infrastructure, and funding sources, without the support of competent and committed human resources, the implementation of organizational tasks will not run optimally (Slatad Mabesad, 2019). Thus, human resources are a key factor in determining the success of the implementation of military organizational activities.

Following the transition from the New Order era to the Reformation era, the Indonesian government emphasized the importance of improving the bureaucratic system to create good governance and clean government. One of these improvements was carried out through bureaucratic reform within the Indonesian Army (TNI AD), with a focus on improving the quality and integrity of human resources based on Pancasila values. Human resources with a high-achieving mentality and high morals will produce superior performance and support the achievement of the organization's vision (Mabesad, 2019).

In the context of the Army Headquarters organization, the role of each staff member has specific responsibilities. Based on the Regulation of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number 26 of 2019, there are several main units under the Army Headquarters, including the Army Inspectorate General (Itjenad), Planning and Budget Staff (Srenaad), Personnel Staff (Spersad), Logistics Staff (Slogad), Intelligence Staff (Sintelad), and Training Staff (Slatad). Each of these units has the function of supervising, planning, developing, and managing human resources, logistics, and intelligence to support the implementation of the main tasks of the Indonesian Army (Itjenad, 2019; Srenaad, 2019; Slogad, 2019).

The performance of military organizations is determined not only by structural factors and resources, but also by the leadership style applied. Transformational leadership is a crucial factor in inspiring, motivating, and directing personnel to achieve organizational goals. Transformational leaders are able to transform organizational values, vision, and culture through role models and coaching oriented toward positive change (Fries et al., 2021). According to Islam et al. (2021), four key traits that influence leadership effectiveness in organizations include intellectual ability, social maturity, self-motivation, and the ability to build healthy personal relationships.

In addition to leadership, knowledge management is also a strategic element supporting organizational performance. Through knowledge management, organizations are able to manage explicit and tacit knowledge to enhance personnel capabilities in facing strategic challenges (Khan et al., 2024). Knowledge is a combination of ideas, experiences, procedures, and values that are considered valid and used to guide actions, thinking, and decision-making within an organizational context. In the military environment, knowledge management is a crucial factor in enhancing an organization's adaptive, innovative, and competitive capabilities.

Another equally important factor is strategic policy, which serves as a guideline for program implementation, leadership, and organizational management. Strategic policy serves as a guide in formulating strategic steps to ensure organizational activities align with the vision, mission, and objectives of the work unit (Putera et al., 2022). A good strategic policy must be oriented toward efficiency and effectiveness, and be able to adapt to rapid changes in the external environment.

The successful implementation of transformational leadership, strategic policies, and knowledge management depends heavily on the organizational commitment of all personnel. Organizational commitment reflects an individual's level of identification, involvement, and loyalty to the organization they work for (Lee & Kim, 2023). Personnel with high commitment will have a strong sense of responsibility to contribute to and achieve shared goals. In the context of the Army Headquarters, this commitment is crucial to ensure that each personnel works with high dedication for the overall success of the organization.

Facing increasingly rapid changes in the strategic environment, the Army Headquarters needs to strengthen the role of transformational leadership, knowledge management, and strategic policy to improve organizational performance through strengthening organizational commitment as a mediating variable. Through the synergy of these three factors, it is hoped that the Army Headquarters will be able to increase organizational effectiveness, strengthen a culture of professionalism, and maintain the competitiveness of national defense institutions. Therefore, this study was conducted with the title "The Effect of *Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management* on *Organizational Performance* of the Army Headquarters Mediated by *Organizational Commitment*."

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a leadership style oriented toward inspiring and motivating followers to transcend their personal interests for the benefit of the organization. Wang et al. (2021) define leadership as an individual's ability to anticipate change, think strategically, and maintain flexibility to create a sustainable organizational future. In this context, leaders act as prime movers who direct the organization's overall behavior. Abdelwahed et al. (2023) add that transformational leadership involves a dynamic relationship between leaders and followers, in which leaders act as facilitators of value exchange and rewards for optimal performance. Baskoro (2022) states that effective leadership must prioritize positive behavior, reward desired performance, and create discipline against deviant behavior. Furthermore, Syaharudin et al. (2022) emphasize that transformational leaders function as agents of change who

can significantly influence the motivation and performance of organizational members.

Transformational leadership also plays a role in shaping a competitive and change-adaptive corporate culture (Erdel & Takka, 2020). Visionary leaders, in this context, are able to create a vision of the future and communicate it to organizational members to encourage the active involvement of all elements (Abdelwahed et al., 2023). According to Alarabiat and Eyupoglu (2022), this type of leadership requires anticipatory skills, flexibility, and the delegation of strategic authority to create sustainable change. Norena-Chavez and Thalassinos (2022) highlight the importance of six components of effective strategic leadership, including clarity of vision, organizational flexibility, and a strong culture of innovation. Thus, transformational leadership not only motivates individuals but also fosters the creation of organizational competitive advantage.

The main dimensions of transformational leadership include *contingent rewards*, *management by exception (active)*, and *individualized consideration* (Hoai et al., 2022). These dimensions reflect a leader's ability to reward performance, take corrective action on deviations, and provide personalized attention to subordinates. According to Baskoro (2022), a contingent reward system strengthens employee motivation and loyalty, while individualized attention increases a sense of commitment to the organization.

b. Strategic Policy

Strategic policy is defined as a series of fundamental and comprehensive decision-making activities within an organization (González, 2023). Strategic policy serves as the primary guideline for an organization to effectively achieve its vision and mission. According to Beckett-Camarata (2020), organizational policy strategy encompasses three main aspects: business strategy, organizational strategy, and information strategy. These three aspects must be harmoniously integrated for a company to adapt to changes in the global environment. Lazarevic et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of aligning strategic and operational policies in achieving organizational effectiveness.

In the context of information technology, Arif Haryana (2022) explains that strategic policy plays a role in establishing an IT governance framework, including planning, risk management, and information resource control. Dühr (2024) adds that the formulation of strategic IT policies must be directed at positioning the information technology function as the primary driver of a company's business value creation. Thus, strategic policy becomes a crucial tool for organizations in aligning human resources, technology, and business strategy to achieve competitive advantage.

Strategic policy dimensions include *team orientation*, *organizational focus*, and *people management* (Beckett-Camarata, 2020). These dimensions emphasize teamwork, organizational focus on long-term goals, and

individual management to achieve policy effectiveness. González (2023) emphasized that an integrated strategic policy will generate synergy between organizational units and strengthen a collaborative culture.

c. Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is a strategic approach focused on creating, storing, and utilizing knowledge to improve organizational performance. Abubakar et al. (2019) stated that knowledge sharing among organizational members is key to successful innovation and performance improvement. Alvarenga et al. (2020) emphasized that implementing knowledge management enables organizations to manage intellectual resources and create sustainable competitive advantage. According to Friedrich et al. (2020), an effective knowledge management strategy requires the integration of technology, organizational structure, and a learning culture that supports collaboration.

From a practical perspective, Bratianu et al. (2021) define knowledge management strategy as strategic decisions regarding the principles and direction of knowledge management. This process encompasses the acquisition, conversion, and application of knowledge (Yee et al., 2019). Dimensions of knowledge management include *altruistic behavior*, *emotional healing*, *wisdom*, and *persuasive mapping* (Duarte Alonso et al., 2022), which describe a leader's ability to foster a spirit of sharing, build emotional intelligence, and instill the value of wisdom in decision-making.

d. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment refers to the extent to which employees identify with the goals and values of the organization and desire to maintain membership (Loan, 2020). Lee and Kim (2023) added that organizational commitment reflects emotional involvement, identification with goals, and loyalty to the organization. Wongsuwan et al. (2023) classify organizational commitment into three dimensions: *affective commitment*, *continuance commitment*, and *normative commitment*. Affective commitment relates to emotional attachment, continuance commitment relates to consideration of the costs of leaving the organization, while normative commitment relates to a sense of moral obligation to remain.

According to Yang and Li (2023), strong organizational commitment drives increased work motivation, satisfaction, and employee desire to contribute more to the organization's success. Therefore, developing organizational commitment is a crucial aspect of creating a productive and sustainable work culture.

e. Organizational Performance

Organizational performance reflects the results of an organization's work in achieving its strategic goals through the effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity of its resources (Abubakar et al., 2019). Aina and Atan (2020) state that

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measuring organizational performance must consider financial aspects, internal processes, learning, and customer satisfaction as contained in *the Balanced Scorecard*. According to Wiraeus and Creelman (2019), dimensions of organizational performance include *financial performance, internal business processes, customer satisfaction, and learning & growth*.

Bhatiasevi and Naglis (2020) added that organizational performance is the result of a process measured against specific targets and indicators over a specific time period. Therefore, organizational performance is measured not only by final results but also through work

processes and behaviors that support the achievement of organizational goals.

This research is built on the basis of theoretical studies and empirical studies that test the influence of *transformational leadership, strategic policy and knowledge management on organizational performance*. Army Headquarters Mediated by *Organizational Commitment*. The main focus of this framework is to understand how *Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management* contribute to improving *Organizational Performance* through effective *Organizational Commitment management*. The framework is illustrated below.

Sumber: Data Olahan (2025)

METHODOLOGY

a. Research Design

This research employed a quantitative method with a positivistic approach, where data was collected through questionnaires distributed to respondents. This quantitative method was chosen because it allows researchers to objectively measure relationships between variables and test hypotheses through statistical calculations. According to Fadli (2021), quantitative methods are based on the philosophy of positivism and are used to examine the conditions of natural objects, with the researcher as the primary instrument. Data collection techniques are systematic, and the analysis focuses more on meaning than generalization.

In this study, quantitative methods were used to uncover and test empirical evidence related to transformational leadership (Dukhaykh et al., 2024), strategic policy (Lurong Chen, 2024), and knowledge management (Durst, 2024) on organizational performance (Nguyen et al., 2023), with organizational commitment (Ibrahim et al., 2023) as a mediating variable. This study aims to describe and explain the causal relationship between variables through

statistical hypothesis testing, resulting in the acceptance or rejection of the proposed hypothesis (Hair et al., 2021).

b. Operational Definition of Variables and Their Measurement

The variables in this study consist of independent, mediating, and dependent variables. The independent variables include transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management. The mediating variable is organizational commitment, while the dependent variable is organizational performance. Each variable is described in its operational definition, dimensions, and indicators measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) as suggested by Hair et al. (2021).

Transformational Leadership

transformational leadership variable is adapted from Dukhaykh et al. (2024), who define transformational leadership as a relationship between leaders and followers that creates a positive influence on organizational performance through motivation, creativity, and innovation. This variable is measured through three dimensions: *contingent reward, active management by exception, and individualized consideration*, with six statement indicators

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describing how leaders provide encouragement, attention, and appreciation for subordinates' achievements.

Strategic Policy

strategic policy variable refers to a concept proposed by Lurong Chen (2024), namely the fundamental and comprehensive decision-making process that drives the entire organization's strategy. This variable has three dimensions: *team orientation*, *organizational focus*, and *people management*, each of which is measured through six indicators to assess the extent to which strategic policies influence organizational effectiveness.

Knowledge Management

knowledge management variable refers to Durst (2024), who defines it as the process of acquiring, converting, and applying knowledge within an organization. Knowledge management is measured using three dimensions: *altruistic*, *emotional*, and *persuasive*, with six indicators assessing the extent to which an organization is able to manage and utilize knowledge effectively.

Organizational Commitment

organizational commitment variable was adapted from Ibrahim et al. (2023) and serves as a mediating variable. This variable reflects the level of emotional attachment, continuance, and employee norms toward the organization. Three dimensions are measured: *affective commitment*, *continuance commitment*, and *normative commitment*, with a total of six statement indicators.

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is the dependent variable in this study. According to Nguyen et al. (2023), organizational performance is the organization's ability to achieve goals effectively and efficiently through resource utilization. This variable is measured using three dimensions: *work productivity*, *work quality*, and *cooperative-social skills*, each of which is described in six statement indicators.

c. Population, Sample, and Data Collection Methods

The population in this study was personnel from the Indonesian Army Headquarters (Mabesad) , including leadership, service, and executive elements known as principal officers. According to Chuah et al. (2021) and Sarstedt et al. (2020), a population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects with certain characteristics determined by the researcher for study. A population can also be defined as the entire unit of analysis that serves as a data source (Manley et al., 2021).

The sampling technique used was saturated sampling, where all members of the population were used as research samples, namely 179 respondents. This is in accordance with the criteria of Sekaran and Bougie (2018)

that the ideal sample size for quantitative research ranges from 30 to 500 respondents. Of the total questionnaires distributed, 177 questionnaires were returned and could be processed, while the other two could not be used due to incomplete filling.

Data collection used a closed-ended questionnaire containing statements based on indicators for each research variable. Questionnaires were distributed in two ways: personally administered questionnaires, which were administered directly to respondents, and online questionnaires via Google Forms.

d. Data Analysis Methods

Data analysis in this study used two stages, namely descriptive statistical analysis and inferential analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Squares (PLS) version 3.30.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used to provide an overview of respondent characteristics, such as gender, age, education, position, and length of service. Data was presented in tabular and percentage form for easy understanding and interpretation (Hair et al., 2021).

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

SEM techniques are used to examine the relationships between variables in the research model. SEM allows for the simultaneous analysis of complex relationships between exogenous and endogenous latent variables (constructs). Model testing is conducted by assessing the validity and reliability of the instrument, where reliability criteria are indicated by a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.70 , a loading factor value > 0.5 , and an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2021). The exogenous constructs in this study include transformational leadership, strategic policy, and knowledge management, while the endogenous construct is organizational performance, with organizational commitment acting as a mediating variable. This analysis aims to explain the causal relationship between variables that influence organizational performance improvement within the Army Headquarters environment.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Hypothesis Testing Results

Based on the results of data processing, it can be concluded that the research hypothesis testing focuses on the *Original Sample (O)* value, which is the *Estimate (Path Coefficient) value*, and *P-Values*. A hypothesis is considered accepted if the *P-Values* obtained are < 0.05 . The results of the hypothesis test from this research model are as follows:

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Hypothesis Test Results

Track		<i>estimate</i>	<i>p-values</i>	Conclusion
<i>α->β Direct</i>				
H1	<i>Transformational leadership -> organizational performance</i>	0,137	0.041	<i>H1: supported</i>
H2	<i>Strategic policy-> organizational performance</i>	0.194	0,000	<i>H2: supported</i>
H3	<i>Knowledge management-> organizational performance</i>	0.265	0,000	<i>H3: supported</i>
H4	<i>Organizational commitment -> organizational performance</i>	0.356	0,000	<i>H4: supported</i>
H5	<i>Transformational leadership -> organizational commitment</i>	0.203	0.003	<i>H5: supported</i>
H6	<i>Strategic policy -> organizational commitment</i>	0.364	0,000	<i>H6: supported</i>
H7	<i>Knowledge management -> organizational commitment</i>	0.337	0,000	<i>H7: supported</i>
H8	<i>Transformational leadership management -> organizational commitment -> organizational performance</i>	0.073	0.001	<i>H8: supported</i>
H9	<i>Strategic policy -> organizational commitment -> organizational performance</i>	0.130	0,000	<i>H9: supported</i>
H10	<i>Knowledge management -> organizational commitment -> organizational performance</i>	0.120	0.002	<i>H10: supported</i>
Note: $p \leq 0.050$				

Source: Data Processed Using SEM PLS

Based on the results of the analysis using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method based on Partial Least Squares (PLS), the results of the hypothesis testing were obtained as explained below.

The results of testing the first hypothesis (H1) show that *transformational leadership* has a positive and significant effect on *organizational performance* with an estimated value of 0.137 and a *p-value* of 0.041 (<0.05). This means that the higher the implementation of transformational leadership in an organization, the higher the organization's performance. Thus, H1 is supported.

Furthermore, the second hypothesis (H2) which tests the influence of *strategic policy* on *organizational performance* also shows significant results with an estimated value of 0.194 and a *p-value* of 0.000 (<0.05). These results indicate that effective strategic policies significantly contribute to improving organizational performance. Therefore, H2 is accepted.

In the third hypothesis (H3), the influence of *knowledge management* on *organizational performance* was tested and produced an estimated value of 0.265 with a *p-value* of 0.000. This value indicates a positive and significant relationship, meaning that the better the knowledge management in the organization, the higher the organizational performance. Thus, H3 is stated as supported.

Then, the fourth hypothesis (H4) shows that *organizational commitment* has a significant positive effect on *organizational performance* with an estimated value of 0.356 and a *p-value* of 0.000. These results confirm that high organizational commitment from personnel can increase the effectiveness and efficiency of achieving organizational goals. Therefore, H4 is accepted.

Furthermore, for the fifth hypothesis (H5), the results obtained show that *transformational leadership* has a positive effect on *organizational commitment* with an estimated value of 0.203 and a *p-value* of 0.003. This means that transformational leadership style is able to foster a sense of attachment and commitment within organizational members. Thus, H5 is stated to be supported.

The sixth hypothesis (H6) shows that *strategic policy* has a positive and significant effect on *organizational commitment* with an estimated value of 0.364 and a *p-value* of 0.000. This means that implementing appropriate strategic policies can increase member loyalty and commitment to the organization. With these results, H6 is accepted.

Meanwhile, the seventh hypothesis (H7) which tests the influence of *knowledge management* on *organizational commitment* obtained an estimated value of 0.337 and a *p-value* of 0.000, indicating a significant positive influence. This illustrates that the better an organization's ability to

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manage and distribute knowledge, the higher the commitment demonstrated by its members. Therefore, H7 is supported.

For the eighth hypothesis (H8), the results of the analysis show that *transformational leadership* influences *organizational performance* through the mediation of *organizational commitment* with an estimated value of 0.073 and a *p-value* of 0.001. These results indicate a significant indirect effect, where organizational commitment acts as a mediator in strengthening the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance. Thus, H8 is accepted.

The ninth hypothesis (H9) tests the influence of *strategic policy* on *organizational performance* through *organizational commitment* and produces an estimated value of 0.130 with a *p-value* 0.000. These results indicate a significant mediation effect, indicating that effective strategic policies can improve organizational performance by increasing personnel commitment to the organization. Therefore, H9 is stated to be supported.

Finally, the tenth hypothesis (H10) tests the influence of *knowledge management* on *organizational performance* through *organizational commitment* and obtains an estimated value of 0.120 with a *p-value* 0.002. These results indicate that *organizational commitment* significantly mediates the relationship between knowledge management and organizational performance. This means that the better the implementation of knowledge management, the stronger the commitment formed, which ultimately impacts on improving organizational performance. Thus, H10 is declared accepted (supported).

Overall, the test results show that all hypotheses (H1–H10) are accepted, meaning that all relationships between hypothesized variables in this research model are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This confirms that transformational leadership, strategic policies, and knowledge management have both direct and indirect influences on organizational performance through organizational commitment as a mediating variable.

b. Discussion of research results

Based on the research objectives and the results of hypothesis testing, the research results can be explained as follows.

1). The Positive Influence of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Performance

Based on the research results, it is known that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance. This means that the higher the level of transformational leadership implementation in an organization, the higher the level of organizational performance. Transformational leaders have the ability to inspire, motivate, and empower their subordinates to achieve common goals. These research results support the findings of Alarabiat and Eyupoglu (2022), who explained that transformational leadership

reflects the ability to anticipate change, build strategic imagination, maintain flexibility, and delegate authority to organizational members to create needed strategic change. This confirms that transformational leadership can have a direct impact on improving organizational performance through empowerment and the creation of a strong vision.

This finding is further supported by Norena-Chavez and Thalassinos (2022), who asserted that transformational leadership positively impacts organizational performance because effective strategic leadership involves six key components: vision, motivation, values, innovation, strategic thinking, and human resource development. By understanding and implementing these components, leaders are able to deliver innovative and adaptive leadership practices that play a crucial role in maintaining organizational sustainability in the future. Meanwhile, Wang et al. (2021) added that transformational leadership is the ability to think strategically, anticipate the future, and create sustainable change for an organization amidst the dynamics of globalization and the complexity of the global economy.

Furthermore, according to Abdelwahed et al. (2023), transformational leadership also plays a role in building a long-term vision for the organization that is communicated effectively to all members to motivate and commit to achieving strategic goals. Visionary leaders have advantages in creativity and innovation, and are able to foster a sense of ownership of the organization's vision. The results of this study also show that the *contingent reward dimension* obtained a fairly high average value, especially in the indicator of leadership attention to goal achievement and agreement on how to achieve performance targets. This indicates that leadership attention to performance achievement remains an important factor in creating organizational effectiveness, especially within the Army Headquarters environment. Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of strong transformational leadership contributes significantly to driving improvements in organizational performance.

2). The Positive Influence of Strategic Policy on Organizational Performance

The results of the study indicate that strategic policy has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance, meaning that the better the strategic policy implemented, the higher the organizational performance. An effective strategic policy serves as the primary guide for all members of the organization in carrying out its mission and achieving a shared vision. These results support the findings of Zulqarnain et al. (2024) who emphasized that implementing targeted strategic policies is crucial in supporting organizational success, especially in the complex world of business and government. With a well-organized strategy, organizations can more easily direct their resources efficiently to achieve their desired goals.

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According to González (2023), *strategic policy* is a fundamental decision-making process formulated by organizational leaders and implemented comprehensively by all levels to achieve strategic goals. Meanwhile, Lazarevic et al. (2022) emphasize that successful organizations have comprehensive strategic policies integrated with organizational and information strategies. These three strategies must be implemented harmoniously because changes in one dimension will affect the others. Therefore, strategic policy serves as the primary instrument that drives the entire organizational system to remain synchronized and results-oriented.

Research by Arias Gómez and Antošová (2023) supports this view by stating that strategic policy is a mechanism for inter-unit coordination and strategic alliances with other organizations that generate greater synergy and competitive advantage than individual efforts. Similarly, Cordero (2021) asserts that well-planned strategic policies can create sustainable advantages for organizations through inter-divisional synergy and adaptive decision-making.

Based on the descriptive results, the highest average value for the *strategic policy variable* was found in the *organizational focus dimension*, namely the indicator "carrying out tasks in accordance with the quality of organizational policies." This illustrates that all personnel at the Army Headquarters have demonstrated high focus, discipline, and commitment in carrying out their duties in accordance with organizational policies. The implementation of strong and targeted strategic policies is an important foundation in maintaining consistent task implementation and continuously improving organizational performance.

3). The Positive Influence of Knowledge Management on Organizational Performance

The research results show that knowledge management has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance. This means that the better the implementation of knowledge management within an organization, the higher the organization's performance. Knowledge management enables organizations to create, store, share, and utilize knowledge effectively, thereby increasing innovation, efficiency, and competitiveness. These results align with the findings of Al-Dhaafri and Alosani (2020), who stated that the relationship between *knowledge management strategic orientation* and organizational performance is complementary. The synergy between exploratory and exploitative orientations can create sustainable competitive advantage.

According to Abubakar et al. (2019), *knowledge management* also plays a role in building a leadership model that focuses on knowledge and exemplary leadership in creating a culture of knowledge sharing in the workplace. This is crucial for fostering trust between leaders and followers and encouraging innovation at both the individual and organizational levels. Furthermore, Lam et al. (2021)

explain that *knowledge management* encompasses values such as *altruistic calling*, *emotional healing*, and *organizational learning*, which help organizations create a productive and learning-oriented work environment.

Meanwhile, Zheng et al. (2020) emphasized that the balanced application of *tacit* and *explicit knowledge* can *strengthen an organization's strategic orientation and reduce operational costs by increasing work efficiency and effectiveness. The implementation of an organizational learning culture that supports the exploration and exploitation of knowledge is also a key factor in maintaining organizational competitiveness. Based on the results of descriptive analysis, the knowledge management variable shows a high average value on the fairness dimension*, which means the institution has fair and wise policies in managing and implementing new policies to support improved organizational performance. Thus, *knowledge management capability* can be seen as an organization's dynamic capability to create, transform, and integrate knowledge resources to improve organizational effectiveness in the future.

4). The Positive Influence of Organizational Commitment on Organizational Performance

Based on the research results, it is known that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance. This indicates that the higher the level of organizational commitment possessed by personnel, the higher the resulting organizational performance. These results align with research by Yang and Li (2023), which states that organizational commitment is a psychological construct that describes the characteristics of the relationship between an individual and their organization and has direct implications for an individual's decision to remain part of the organization. Thus, individuals who have a strong emotional bond and sense of belonging to the organization will strive to provide their best contribution.

This research also supports the findings of Nabhan and Munajat (2023), who asserted that organizational commitment reflects an individual's emotional attachment, involvement, and loyalty to their organization. This commitment serves as a key driver in improving performance, as highly dedicated organizational members tend to be oriented toward achieving shared goals. A similar sentiment was expressed by Ibrahim et al. (2023), who emphasized that organizational commitment contains elements of togetherness and loyalty that strengthen the relationship between employees and their institutions.

Furthermore, Aranki et al. (2019) outlined that organizational commitment consists of three main dimensions: commitment to organizational goals, involvement in organizational activities, and loyalty to the organization. These three dimensions simultaneously drive improved organizational performance through active participation and employee willingness to exert extra effort at work. According to Loan (2020), organizational commitment

is also closely related to the level of employee desire to continue participating in the organization and contributing to its success.

Empirically, the results of this study indicate that the continuance commitment dimension achieved the highest average score, particularly for the indicator indicating that personnel have a high level of trust in the organization and would find it difficult to leave. This indicates that emotional attachment and trust in the organization are important factors in strengthening organizational performance, particularly in a military environment that emphasizes loyalty, discipline, and devotion to the institution.

5). The Positive Influence of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Commitment

The research results show that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This means that the greater the leader's ability to implement a transformational leadership style, the stronger the members' commitment to the organization. This finding aligns with the research of Alarabiat and Eyupoglu (2022), which explains that transformational leadership can increase subordinate loyalty and dedication because leaders not only provide direction but also serve as inspiration and role models for their followers.

According to Egel (2021), transformational leaders guide and optimize the potential of their subordinates and treat them fairly. This type of leadership fosters trust, fairness, and intrinsic motivation, ultimately strengthening commitment to the organization. Furthermore, Ibrahim et al. (2023) also emphasized that a leadership style oriented toward vision, strategy, and employee empowerment can increase emotional engagement and attachment to the organization.

This finding is reinforced by research by Nabhan and Munajat (2023), who stated that transformational leadership can shape a competitive and positive organizational culture, thus becoming a strategic resource for fostering high levels of commitment. Meanwhile, Eseryel et al. (2021) found that leaders with a clear vision and the ability to effectively utilize technology can strengthen learning and knowledge management processes, leading to increased commitment.

According to Loan (2020), transformational leadership behavior will create a work climate that supports employee learning and development. Leaders play a crucial role in creating a conducive work environment, where each member feels valued and has meaning in their role. Empirically, the results of this study indicate that the continuance commitment dimension also ranks highest, indicating that loyalty and trust in the organization grow from an inspirational and empowerment-oriented leadership style.

6). The Positive Influence of Strategic Policy on Organizational Commitment

The research results show that strategic policy has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This means that the better the implementation of strategic policy within the organization, the stronger the members' commitment to the organization. These results support research by González (2023), which states that strategic policy is a synergistic interaction between units within an organization that produces greater performance results than if they worked individually.

According to Dühr (2024), strategic policies encompass the utilization of organizational resources, such as knowledge, human, and physical assets, to generate sustainable market value. Planned and long-term policy implementation can increase the sense of responsibility and engagement of organizational members in achieving shared goals. Furthermore, Arif Haryana (2022) explains that properly managed organizational resources can determine an organization's competitive success and strengthen internal commitment.

These findings are further supported by Lurong Chen (2024), who emphasized that strategic policies serve as guidelines for utilizing organizational assets such as expertise, processes, and information to achieve greater effectiveness and efficiency. According to Vonoga (2022), strategic policies also play a role in strengthening teamwork, effective problem-solving, and participatory decision-making. If these policies are consistently implemented, they will foster a collaborative culture that strengthens organizational loyalty and commitment.

However, this study also noted that the team orientation dimension received the lowest score, indicating ongoing challenges in understanding the roles and functions of each individual in the field due to job rotation and differences in leadership styles. Therefore, improving understanding of strategic policies and adaptive leadership training need to be a priority to continuously improve organizational commitment.

7). The Positive Influence of Knowledge Management on Organizational Commitment

Based on the research results, it is known that *knowledge management* has a significant and positive effect on *organizational commitment*. This means that the better the implementation of *knowledge management* in an organization, the higher the level of organizational commitment formed among its members. This result is in line with research by Quansah et al. (2022) which found that *knowledge management* has a positive influence on *organizational commitment*. Systematically managed knowledge is a determining factor in organizational effectiveness in building strong connections between human resources, technology, business processes, and business opportunities, which ultimately increases economic, social,

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and intellectual value for all stakeholders. Thus, *knowledge management* not only plays a role in operational efficiency but also strengthens employees' sense of belonging and loyalty to the organization.

Furthermore, Singh et al. (2023) explain that great groups *are* formed from the collaboration of organizational members who are able to share knowledge and are accountable for collective performance results. In this context, *knowledge management* becomes a platform for collective learning processes where organizational members can utilize internal and external information to increase engagement and commitment to the organization. Meanwhile, Bratianu et al. (2021) emphasize that effective *knowledge management practices* will strengthen the emotional bond between employees and the organization because each individual feels they have a strategic contribution to the organization's success.

Research by Ucar and Dalgic (2021) also shows that the relationship between humans and technological systems in *knowledge management* requires strong organizational commitment from leaders and all members. In modern organizations, especially those based on technology and information, the successful implementation of *knowledge management* depends on strategic leadership that balances business strategy with human resource management. This research finding is further supported by empirical evidence showing that military personnel demonstrate adaptive capabilities to technological and information developments, reflecting a strong organizational commitment to continuous learning and individual capability development.

8). The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Performance Mediated by Organizational Commitment

The results of the study indicate that *transformational leadership* has a positive and significant effect on *organizational performance* through the mediation of *organizational commitment*. This means that effective transformational leadership can improve organizational performance by strengthening its members' commitment to the organization's vision and goals. This research supports the findings of Rasheed et al. (2021), who explained that *transformational leadership practices* can be an important medium in translating knowledge sharing capabilities into optimal performance outcomes. In this context, innovation and human resource management are two key factors that strengthen the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance.

Firmansyah et al. (2022) added that transformational leadership is rooted in *tacit knowledge* within individual leaders, which plays a crucial role in facilitating knowledge growth and the development of leadership values within the organization. This view aligns with Hai et al. (2021), who assert that transformational leaders not only direct but also inspire organizational members to think creatively, innovate,

and optimize their potential. According to Kaur Bagga et al. (2023), this positive influence is reinforced by strategic human resource management practices, such as training, reward systems, and the creation of a collaborative learning culture. All of these factors contribute to increased *organizational commitment*, which ultimately improves organizational performance.

Descriptive results indicate that personnel are given the opportunity to improve their skills in science and technology and gain access to integrated information systems within the organization. This confirms that *transformational leadership* within the Army Headquarters plays a crucial role in creating a work climate that supports increased competence and active participation of organizational members. However, challenges remain in terms of suboptimal coordination and distribution of responsibilities, necessitating improved internal communication for effective implementation of organizational policies. This finding aligns with research by Son et al. (2020) which emphasizes the importance of human capital and leadership knowledge in driving innovation and sustainable organizational performance by strengthening *organizational commitment*.

9). The Influence of Strategic Policy on Organizational Performance Mediated by Organizational Commitment

Based on the research results, it was found that *strategic policy* has a positive and significant effect on *organizational performance* through the mediation of *organizational commitment*. This means that well-designed strategic policies can improve organizational performance by strengthening members' commitment to achieving organizational goals. This research is consistent with Gale's (2021) findings, which explain that *strategic policy* contributes to organizational readiness for change because strategic policies can increase employee confidence in the effectiveness of the change process and its ability to support the achievement of shared goals.

Demir et al. (2023) emphasized that organizational readiness for change is a critical factor influencing the successful implementation of strategic policies. This readiness depends on the level of employee commitment and involvement in the change process. Tjahjadi et al. (2021) also found that successful organizational change requires an active role for leaders in fostering a *readiness for change attitude* among employees, enabling them to adapt and work synergistically to achieve optimal performance. Furthermore, Jarrahi et al. (2023) explained that *organizational commitment* is a crucial link between strategic policies and organizational performance because highly committed individuals tend to exhibit voluntary behaviors such as helping coworkers, following rules, and engaging in additional tasks beyond formal descriptions.

Field research also shows weaknesses in the *team orientation dimension*, particularly in eliminating sectoral

egos to achieve shared goals. This highlights the need for leadership to prioritize strengthening cross-departmental collaboration and enhancing understanding of the roles and functions of each individual within the organization. This supports Hashim's (2020) research, which states that implementing generic strategies such as cost leadership or differentiation can improve organizational performance when coupled with strong organizational commitment. Therefore, an effective *strategic policy* emphasizes more than just strategy formulation; it also requires strong commitment and coordination among all members of the organization to achieve shared success.

10). The Influence of Knowledge Management on Organizational Performance Mediated by Organizational Commitment

The results of the study indicate that *knowledge management* has a positive and significant effect on *organizational performance*, mediated by *organizational commitment*. This means that the more effective the implementation of *knowledge management*, the higher the organizational performance through increased employee commitment to the organization. This study supports the findings of Zheng et al. (2020), who proposed that *knowledge management control systems* contribute to the positive relationship between *organizational commitment* and *organizational performance*. In other words, organizations that are able to manage knowledge effectively will increase employee loyalty, which ultimately impacts performance improvement.

Chaithanapat et al. (2022) also found that in the dynamic digital era, *organizational commitment* plays a crucial role as a mediator in the relationship between *knowledge management* and *organizational performance*. The better the knowledge management within an organization, the stronger the commitment of its members to work productively and collaboratively. Meanwhile, Bratianu et al. (2021) emphasized that the complementary management of *tacit* and *explicit knowledge* can optimize organizational strategy and reduce operational costs. Ammirato et al. (2021) added that a culture of continuous learning and training is a crucial element in strengthening *knowledge management* to positively impact organizational performance.

In the context of the Army Headquarters, the highest score was found in the *cooperative social skills dimension*, indicating that technological resources have been met to support personnel capacity building. This demonstrates that technology investment plays a significant role in strengthening organizational performance. However, the lowest average score for the same dimension indicates persistent weaknesses in personnel's ability to collectively improve organizational performance. Furthermore, in the *normative commitment dimension*, it was found that some personnel work out of moral obligation, rather than out of

emotional attachment to the organization. Therefore, increasing normative commitment through mental development and achievement-based rewards needs to be continuously implemented so that the Army Headquarters can become an example of a superior and sustainable knowledge-based organization.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, Knowledge Management, and Organizational Commitment have a significant positive influence on Organizational Performance at the Army Headquarters. This influence occurs both directly and indirectly through the mediating variable Organizational Commitment, with Transformational Leadership showing the strongest influence. The role of Organizational Commitment as a mediator has proven effective in strengthening the impact of Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management on organizational performance.

In detail, Transformational Leadership provides a significant contribution to Organizational Performance because leaders at the Army Headquarters are able to influence decision-making, provide solutions, and improve the capabilities of officers and officials in various units, thereby creating optimal organizational performance. Strategic Policy also has a positive influence, because the implementation of appropriate strategic policies can increase the enthusiasm and readiness of all organizational personnel in achieving the best results. Knowledge Management has been proven to improve the quality and capabilities of personnel, thereby supporting organizational progress through the effective use of information and technology.

Organizational Commitment also plays an important role in improving organizational performance, because personnel commitment to the position and selection based on performance and leadership considerations creates honest, directed, and consistent performance. Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management each have a positive effect on Organizational Commitment, indicating that effective leadership, appropriate policies, and good knowledge management will strengthen personnel loyalty, motivation, and attachment to the organization.

Furthermore, the influence of Transformational Leadership, Strategic Policy, and Knowledge Management on Organizational Performance is further strengthened when mediated by Organizational Commitment. This demonstrates the crucial role of mediators in ensuring that leadership, policy, and knowledge management are optimally translated into high organizational performance. Therefore, improving leadership quality, implementing strategic policies, managing knowledge effectively, and maintaining high personnel commitment are key to achieving superior Organizational Performance at the Army Headquarters.

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Overall, this study confirms that the synergy between transformational leadership, strategic policies, knowledge management, and organizational commitment is an important foundation in improving the performance and effectiveness of military organizations, and can be used as a reference for developing the capacity and quality of resources at the Army Headquarters.

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